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Teachers' Mindset Engaged in Teaching Foreign Language

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Abstract

The study provides a detailed examination of teachers' mindset engaged in teaching foreign languages, as well as the impact of teachers' knowledge of mindset on classroom teaching practises and their subsequent impact on students' academic success. Because of the potential consequences for student learning and achievement, the idea of mindset, particularly the distinction between fixed and growth mindsets, has received significant attention in the field of education. It is critical to understand how teachers' knowledge and beliefs about mindset impact their instructional approaches in order to provide an ideal learning environment in the classroom. Knowledge of mindset can provide a clue to adopting correct teaching methodologies, necessary feedback, and praises to promote growth mindset in order to keep intrinsic motivation to establish learning environment among students. It can even raise awareness regarding instructional language and foster a supportive and growth-oriented learning environment within the curriculum.

Keywords: Mindset, Fixed mindset, Growth mindset, Instructional practices, Feedback, Praises, Learning environment, Motivation

1. Introduction

The research involves gathering data from a semi-structured questionnaire on teacher mindset awareness, as well as related studies on the relationship between teacher mindset awareness and teaching practise. It explores how instructors' beliefs and mindsets can influence classroom instruction in a variety of ways, including feedback types, language used in instruction, and fostering a supportive and growth-oriented learning environment.

Furthermore, the research is aimed into how knowing teachers' mindsets might influence student motivation and learning results. It examines studies that demonstrates the positive influence of teachers who promote a growth mindset by providing constructive feedback, promoting effort, and reinforcing kids' potential to progress with dedication and persistence. Furthermore, the research looks at various challenges and constraints that instructors may face while applying metacognitive strategies in the classroom. It highlights the need of continual professional development and assisting instructors in better understanding and effectively integrating theories of mindset into their instructional strategies. Furthermore, the research is aimed into how knowing teachers' mindsets might influence student motivation and learning results. It examines studies that demonstrates the positive influence of teachers who promote a growth mindset by providing constructive feedback, promoting effort, and reinforcing kids' potential to progress with dedication and persistence. Furthermore, the research looks at various challenges and constraints that instructors may face while applying metacognitive strategies in the classroom. It highlights the need of continual professional development and

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assisting instructors in better understanding and effectively integrating theories of mindset into their instructional strategies.

The significance of teachers' mindsets in structuring classroom instruction and enhancing academic achievement is highlighted in this study. This emphasises the need of teacher education programmes and professional development opportunities that emphasise thinking theories, as well as the implementation of thinking-related practises into curriculum design and teaching practices. Educators may create an environment that develops students' potential and improves their overall academic success by harnessing the power of a growth mindset. The significance of teachers' mindsets in structuring classroom instruction and enhancing academic achievement is highlighted in this study. This emphasises the need of teacher education programmes and professional development opportunities that emphasise thinking theories, as well as the implementation of thinking-related practises into curriculum design and teaching practices. Educators may create an environment that develops students' potential and improves their overall academic success by harnessing the power of a growth mindset.

2. *Mindset*

There are two types of mindsets: fixed mindset and growth mindset. A growth mindset acknowledges that intelligence and abilities may be improved by dedicated practise and motivation, whereas a fixed mindset believes that these traits are natural and unchangeable. According to Dweck's (2006) research, persons with a growth mindset are more willing to embrace difficulties and persevere when things don't go their way. Blackwell, Trzesniewski, and Dweck (2007) research claims that students who have a growth mindset perform better academically than those who have a fixed perspective.

According to Dweck and colleagues' (2007) research, students with a fixed mindset—who regard intelligence as a fixed trait—are more likely to suffer academically. Blackwell, Trzesniewski, and Dweck (2007) discovered that students with a growth mindset were more likely to apply effective learning approaches and achieve higher levels of academic achievement. According to research, having a fixed mindset can make it more difficult to perform in school (Burnette et al., 2013). When confronted with difficult activities, students who believe their intellect is fixed are more likely to avoid them and to give up easily (Burnette et al. 2013). Yeager and Dweck (2012) found that students that have a growth mindset are more likely to persevere in tough academic settings, apply efficient learning strategies, and get higher grades. Promoting a growth mindset through interventions has improved students' academic performance. Students who received a growth mindset intervention improved their grades and test scores (Paunesku et al., 2015). According to research, a person's thinking has a significant impact on how well they do. Mueller and Dweck (1998) discovered, for example, that students

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with a development mentality performed better on academic tasks than those with a fixed mindset.

According to Haimovitz and Dweck (2016) research, students with a growth mindset are more likely to engage in deeper levels of learning, see barriers as chances for learning, and keep intrinsic motivation throughout the course. Students can be motivated and engaged in intensive study by developing a growth mindset. According to Paunesku et al. (2015), students who participated in a mindset intervention programme improved their academic performance. Students who adopt a growth mindset are more likely to achieve higher grades and persevere in the face of challenge than those who embrace a fixed mindset (Dweck et al. 2011). In another study, college students with a growth mindset were more likely than those with a fixed mindset to persist with their studies, obtain better grades, and earn a degree (Claro, Paunesku, and Dweck, 2016). As a result, cultivating a growth mindset culture among students can boost learning. According to Hong et al. (2013), cultural variables can influence students' mindsets and, as a result, their academic achievement. Students from cultures that value work and progress outscored those from countries that respect intrinsic talent more, according to the study.

3. *Mindset and academic success*

Mindset, or individuals' inner beliefs and attitudes about their skills and intelligence, has a significant impact on academic success. A person's mindset can have a significant impact on their approach to learning, motivation, and perseverance in the face of challenges.

People with a growth mindset believe that intelligence and abilities may be developed via hard work, effective strategies, and perseverance. Challenges are regarded as chances for growth and learning, whereas setbacks are perceived as temporary hurdles that may be overcome. As a result, individuals have a more positive attitude about learning, welcome challenges, and exhibit higher levels of motivation and engagement in their academic endeavours (Dweck, 2017; Limeri et al., 2020; Rohne, 2015; Yu & McLellan, 2020). Individuals with a fixed mindset, on the other hand, feel that intelligence and abilities are fixed attributes that cannot be greatly changed. Failures and losses are often interpreted as evidence of a lack of skill, leading to emotions of powerlessness and fear about taking on challenging subjects (Barbouta et al., 2020; Manchi Chao et al., 2017; Nalipay et al., 2021; Sanguras, 2021). This fixed mindset can endanger their academic achievement by reducing their desire to take chances, engage in deep learning, and persevere in the face of difficulty.

Mindset has a significant effect in academic achievement, according to research. Students that have a growth mindset are more likely to set higher goals, use effective learning strategies, and seek feedback and guidance. They exert more effort and resilience, and are more likely to

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recover from failures and setbacks. As a result, they tend to get higher marks, do better on examinations, and have superior overall academic achievement. A student's mindset affects other parts of their life, such as motivation, self-confidence, and well-being, in addition to academic performance. Students that have a growth mindset are more likely to like learning, to have a positive self-image, and to have better levels of self-efficacy. They are also more likely to seek out new challenges, take on new possibilities, and develop essential lifelong learning skills.

Educators can help students develop a growth mindset. They can help students develop a growth mindset by encouraging students to believe in the malleability of intelligence and abilities, as well as by providing feedback and praise that emphasises effort, progress, and effective tactics (Yeager et al., 2019). Creating a supportive learning environment that encourages risk-taking, fosters a passion of learning, and recognises mistakes as learning opportunities can help to foster a growth mindset and contribute to increased academic achievement. Educators can demonstrate a growth mindset for students to help them develop it. They can help students in creating a growth mindset by establishing faith in the malleability of intelligence and abilities, as well as providing feedback and appreciation that emphasises effort, progress, and effective strategies (Yeager et al., 2019). Creating a supportive learning environment that encourages risk-taking, fosters a love of learning, and recognises mistakes as learning opportunities can aid in the development of a growth mindset and contribute to academic success.

Academic success is strongly predicted by mindset. A growth mindset, defined by the belief in one's ability for growth and development, leads to increased motivation, engagement, and resilience in the face of difficulty. A fixed mindset, on the other hand, can hinder students' willingness to take chances and persevere in the face of difficulties. Educators and parents may inspire students to fulfil their full potential and achieve academic success by creating a growth mindset.

4. Implication of feedback and praises on mindset

Individuals' mindsets are shaped through feedback, praise, rewards and implicit meaning hidden in social interaction, which can have significant implications for their personal growth, development, and academic performance. The manner in which comments and appreciation are presented can either reinforce growth mindset or promote a fixed mindset.

Feedback that is entirely focused on fixed traits or talents, such as telling someone they are "clever" or "talented," might develop a fixed attitude. Individuals who hear this type of feedback may develop the misconception that their abilities are fixed and unchangeable. As a result, they may avoid challenges, become frustrated by setbacks, and rely on external

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validation to feel competent (Cui, 2021; C. Dweck, 2019; Hochanadel & Finamore, 2015; Li & Bates, 2019; Wormeli, 2018). Feedback that stresses effort, strategy, and progress, on the other hand, might foster a growth mindset. Individuals are more likely to develop a belief that their abilities can be developed through dedication and hard work when feedback focuses on specific actions, progress, and areas for growth (Hong & Oh, 2020; Rissanen et al., 2019; "Supplemental Material for Do Growth Mindset Interventions Impact Students' Academic Achievement? A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis with Best Practice Recommendations," 2022; Wang et al., 2018). This form of feedback encourages people to see challenges as learning opportunities and to perseverance in the face of difficulties.

Similarly, praises can have a significant impact on one's thinking. Typical praises that simply reinforce fixed characteristics, such as telling someone they are "naturally talented," might unintentionally encourage a fixed mindset. Specific compliments that appreciate and highlight work, progress, and strategies, on the other hand, can create a growth mindset. Individuals are more likely to acquire a belief in their own abilities to progress and achieve if they are praised for their hard work, persistence, and successful learning strategies (Bostwick et al., 2017; Calingasan & Plata, 2022; C. Dweck, 2019).

The effects of feedback and praise on mindset are significant. Individuals with a growth mindset are more inclined to welcome difficulties, regard failures as learning opportunities, and persevere in the face of setbacks. They are driven to improve their talents, seek feedback, and always improve. Individuals with a fixed mindset, on the other hand, may avoid challenges, reject feedback, and give up easily when presented with difficulties (Earley et al., 1990; Koka & Hein, 2005; Park & Shon, 2020).

Educators and parents play an important role in promoting a growth mindset by offering effective feedback and praise. They can assist individuals create a belief in their own potential to learn and improve by focusing on effort, progress, and particular strategies. As a result, their motivation, engagement, and overall outlook may improve. Individuals' mindsets are profoundly influenced by feedback and praise. Educators and parents can encourage a growth mindset in individuals by providing feedback that emphasises effort, progress, and improvement, as well as specific praise that recognises hard work and effective solutions. This can have serious consequences for their motivation, resilience, and academic achievement.

5. *Mindset and motivation*

Mindset and motivation are inextricably linked characteristics that influence people's attitudes, behaviours, and overall performance. Mindset refers to an individual's thoughts and attitudes toward their own skills and the possibilities for growth and development. Motivation, on the other hand, refers to the internal and external factors that drive people's behaviour, effort, and

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persistence in reaching their goals (C. S. Dweck, 2017; Manchi Chao et al., 2017; Rohne, 2015; Sanguras, 2021).

A growth mindset is closely related with intrinsic motivation since it is defined by the concept that abilities may be developed through dedication and hard work. Individuals with a growth mindset are intrinsically motivated, which means that they are motivated by internal factors such as genuine interest in the task, a desire to learn, and a sense of personal satisfaction (C. Dweck, 2019; Sheffler et al., 2022; Yeager & Dweck, 2012; Zhao et al., 2018). They see problems as growth opportunities and are more likely to embrace them, persevere in the face of failures, and seek out learning opportunities. Individuals with a fixed mindset, on the other hand, who believe that abilities are fixed and cannot be modified considerably, may be more responsive to extrinsic motivation. Extrinsic motivation refers to the external elements that influence people's conduct, such as rewards, praise, or recognition (Bieg et al., 2011; C. S. Dweck, 1986; Kormos et al., 2011). While extrinsic motivation can be useful in some situations, people with a fixed mindset may become overly reliant on external rewards and seek acceptance from others instead of being driven by their own internal desires (Sutherland, 2005; Tsai, 1991; Wolters & Rosenthal, 2000).

It is important to note that both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation can have an impact on an individual's behaviour and performance. According to research, intrinsic motivation is more conducive to long-term engagement, deeper learning, and long-term success (Elliot & Harackiewicz, 1996; Katsuhisa & Masahide, 2009; Rawsthorne & Elliot, 1999). Intrinsic motivation develops a sense of autonomy, competence, and relatedness, which are all required for individuals to develop a genuine passion for their efforts and sustain their motivation over time. Furthermore, mindset has a big impact on people's motivation. A growth mindset is related with increased self-efficacy, or belief in one's own potential to succeed, which supports intrinsic motivation. Individuals with a growth mindset are more inclined to set challenging goals, put out effort, and persevere in the face of difficulty because they see failures as chances for learning and improvement (Davies et al., 2015; Deci & Ryan, 1985; Di Domenico & Ryan, 2017; Sochan, 2012). A fixed mindset, on the other hand, can undermine motivation by instilling a fear of failure, a desire to avoid challenges, and a tendency to give up easily. Individuals with a fixed mindset may be more concerned with gaining approval and avoiding unfavourable judgments than with taking chances and pursuing their goals with intrinsic motivation (Jovanovic & Matejevic, 2014; K. A. Miller et al., 1988; Ng, 2018; Reeve & Deci, 1996).

Mindset and motivation are interconnected factors that have a significant impact on people's attitudes, behaviours, and success. A growth mindset can boost intrinsic motivation, boost self-efficacy, and create a lifetime love of learning and achievement. Educators, parents, and

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individuals may all work together to foster a growth mindset and intrinsic motivation, ultimately unlocking their full potential and attaining meaningful and long-term success.

6. *Teachers' Mindset Survey Analysis*

A semi-structured questionnaire was used to assess teachers' knowledge of mindset. The survey was completed among 16 teachers. Furthermore, data was analysed to investigate teachers' awareness of mindset and its impact on academic success. Data collected from teachers revealed that teachers were unaware of self-theory or implicit theory of intelligence. They had no knowledge that their praise enhanced the students' learnability. They agreed that all forms of compliments serve to inspire and improve students' academic abilities. They even showed that compliments such as "you are intelligent/you are smart/you are talented" always increase positive motivation among students. It boosts the learners' performance. However, it has been thoroughly researched that this type of motivation has a negative impact on students; such compliments place an intelligent tag on them, making them performance goal seekers.

Even though no teacher was aware of the theory of mindset and implicit theory of intelligence and their possible impact on academic success, over half of teachers claimed being aware of the mindset. According to the survey findings, teachers were implicitly encouraging fixed mindset and performance goals among students through praise and feedback because these feedbacks and praises imply fixedness. Because fixed skill and intellect are permanent, students may interpret them implicitly. Students with a fixed mindset are poor learners and intrinsic motivators; when performance expectations are not reached and the talent's image suffers, they develop vulnerabilities and helplessness. They felt helpless, which caused anxiety and stress. Sad messages took control of their minds, altering brain chemicals and putting their mental systems in jeopardy, leaving them in a dreadful situation.

Effect of Feedback on Mindset and academic success: According to Yeager et al. (2019), demonstrated that targeted feedback emphasising the opportunity for development and improvement can alter students' mindsets, leading to enhanced motivation and academic performance. Butler (1988) discovered that feedback that focuses effort, progress, and particular strategies might develop a growth mindset and improve students' academic success. According to Blackwell, Trzesniewski, and Dweck (2007) research, feedback that focuses on effort, strategies, and specific areas for improvement can foster a growth mindset in students and positively influence their academic success. Kluger and DeNisi (1996) discovered in a meta-analysis that feedback that is specific, timely, and offers suggestions for improvement can positively impact students' mindset, self-efficacy, beliefs, and achievement.

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According to a study conducted by Blackwell, Trzesniewski, and Dweck (2007), interventions aimed at teachers to utilise process-oriented praise rather than general praise about intellect led to significant changes in students' mindset, motivation, and academic achievement. Paunesku et al. (2021) discovered that a brief online mindset intervention increased high school students' motivation and academic performance.

Effects of Teacher's feedback and Praise on Mindset and Academic Success: According to research, the kind of praise offered by teachers might influence students' mindsets and academic success (Gunderson et al., 2013). Praise that emphasises effort, strategies, or specific aspects of performance can foster a growth mindset and lead to better academic outcomes. A study (D. I. Miller, 2019; Yeager et al., 2016) found that teaching practises emphasising a growth mindset, such as delivering process-oriented praise, can boost student motivation and academic achievement. According to one study, specific praise focusing on effort, methods, or improvement had a greater positive impact on students' mindset and motivation than generalized praise focused on intelligence or skills (Kamins & Dweck, 1999; Kluger & DeNisi, 1996).

According to Kluger and DeNisi (1996), detailed, relevant feedback that provides direction for growth can significantly influence student thinking and promote academic achievement. Butler (1988) discovered in their research that feedback that emphasises on effort, process, and effective solutions can encourage a growth mindset, boost motivation, and positively improve academic success. Yeager et al. (2019) proved in their study that providing students with feedback that emphasises their abilities' malleability and potential for growth can shape a growth mindset, increase motivation, and improve academic success. Henderlong Corpus and Lepper (2007) discovered that process-oriented praise, which promotes effort, strategies, and specific actions, is related to students' academic motivation and performance.

This research has led to the conclusion that, teachers who are involved in foreign language learning are critical. Several studies have found that those with growth mindsets are better at learning foreign languages. Foreign language, like skill and ability, necessitates regular practise and focused strategies with intrinsic motivation for the learning goal; thus, growth mindset is best suited for this, whereas fixed mindset lacks all of these characteristics (Hu et al., 2022; Khajavy et al., 2021; Liu, 2022).

7. Conclusion

This comprehensive review investigated the teachers' mindsets engaged in teaching foreign language. The findings emphasise how important teachers' mindsets are in affecting their instructional practises, student engagement, and overall learning.

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According to the research, teachers who have a growth mindset are more likely to use successful teaching strategies, provide relevant feedback, and foster a positive learning atmosphere. They see obstacles as opportunities for growth, mistakes as learning opportunities, and believe in the ability of all students to succeed. Such teachers cultivate a positive classroom environment that encourages risk-taking, resilience, and a love of learning. Teachers with a fixed mindset, on the other hand, may be more likely to rely on traditional educational approaches, have low expectations for student advancement, and underestimate the potential for improvement. Their assumptions about fixed talents may inadvertently impede students' growth and demotivate them from learning a foreign language.

The implications of teachers' beliefs toward foreign language teaching are far-reaching. It is critical for teacher education programmes to prioritise educators' development of a growth mindset. This can be achieved through focused professional development, active learning, and the formation of a supportive community of educators who share and promote growth-oriented attitudes.

Furthermore, policymakers and educational institutions need recognise the significance of mindset in foreign language instruction and give teachers with resources and support to develop and maintain a growth mindset. This includes opportunities for cooperation, continued professional development, and fostering a culture of continuous growth and learning in institutions.

We can improve the quality of teaching, student engagement, and language learning outcomes by understanding and addressing the impact of teachers' mindsets on foreign language education. Teachers' perspective is critical not only for their own professional development, but also for their students' success and motivation in gaining foreign language skills.

Finally, establishing a growth mindset in schools can result in more effective language teaching, higher student engagement, and better language learning results. Recognizing the significance of mindset in moulding teaching practises and investing in teachers' mindset development is critical for the benefit of both educators and students in foreign language education.

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